

Nitrato-Complexes of Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) with 2-(2'-Pyridyl)Benzimidazole

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The nitrato-complexes, $[Y(PyBzH)_2(NO_3)_2]NO_3 \cdot H_2O$ and $[Ln(PyBzH)_2NO_3 \cdot OH \cdot H_2O]NO_3 \cdot nH_2O \cdot mC_2H_5OH$ [$Ln=La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho$; $n=1-3$, $m=0-0.5$; $PyBzH=2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole$] are formed on interaction of the ligand with metal nitrates in ethanol. The electrical conductance values ($116-129 \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$) suggest 1:1 electrolyte-nature of the complexes. Magnetic moment values of Ce(2.53 B.M.), Pr(3.62 B.M.), Nd(3.52 B.M.), Sm(1.70 B.M.), Gd(8.06 B.M.), Tb(9.44 B.M.), Dy(10.56 B.M.) and Ho(10.51 B.M.) in the complexes confirm the terpositive state of the metals. Infrared evidences are obtained for the existence of both coordinated (C_{3v}) and uncoordinated (D_{3h}) nitrate groups. Electronic absorption spectra of Pr(III)-, Nd(III)-, Sm(III)-, Tb(III)-, Dy(III)- and Ho(III)-complexes have been analysed in the light of LSJ terms.

THE N-heterocycles, for example, 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) or 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), usually being less basic than most of the amines, are more useful as nitrogen-donors for the lanthanides. The 1,10-phenanthroline complexes of the type $Ln(phen)_3(NO_3)_3$ were reported by Hart *et al*¹ and 2,2'-bipyridyl complexes of the type $Ln(bipy)_3 \cdot (H_2O)_n(NO_3)_3$ by Sinha². The study of these complexes leads one to conclude that aromaticity enhances the chelating ability of the heterocyclic ligands.

The ligand, 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (PyBzH) having the same coordination site, $-N=C-C=N-$, as phen or bipy has been shown in our previous communication³ to form isothiocyanato-complexes of the lanthanides by partial replacement in $Ln(NCS)_3^{2-}$. Here we report the nitrato-complexes of PyBzH with Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III).

Experimental

Preparation of the ligand: 2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazole was prepared by the condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with picolinic acid by the method cited in literature⁴.

Metal nitrates: The hydrated crystals of metal(III) nitrates, obtained from Indian Rare Earths, Kerala, in 99.9-99.99% purity were used as such.

Preparation of the complexes: A mixture of the ethanolic solution of metal nitrate and the ligand in 1:2 molar proportion was refluxed for a few min when a solid started separating; the heavier the metal, the quicker was the separation. The

mixture was refluxed for about 1 hr to ensure complete digestion. The solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with hot ethanol and dried over $CaCl_2$.

Physical measurements: Electrical conductances were measured with Philips PR 9500 Resistance Bridge using dip-type cell, calibrated with KCl solution. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy magnetic balance calibrated⁵ with $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$, diamagnetic corrections being made using Pascal's constants⁶. Infrared spectra were scanned on Beckman IR-12 in KBr discs through commercial services of the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, IIT, Madras. Electronic spectra were recorded on Cary 14 and Cary 17 spectrophotometers using matched silica cells.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: Y(III)-nitrate, on interaction with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole in ethanol, forms the 8-coordinate dinitrato-bis(ligand)yttrium(III) nitrate monohydrate, $[Y(PyBzH)_2(NO_3)_2]NO_3 \cdot H_2O$. The nitrates of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III), however, form the 8-coordinate hydroxo-aquonitrato-complexes of the general formula, $[Ln(PyBzH)_2NO_3 \cdot OH \cdot H_2O]NO_3 \cdot nH_2O \cdot mC_2H_5OH$. Water and/or alcohol of crystallisation is lost by heating upto 120° in each of these complexes and the coordinated water by heating upto 200° . The 1:1 electrolyte nature of the compounds is supported by their electrical conductance values of $116-129 \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ in DMF at 304°K (Table 1).

Magnetic moments: The room-temperature magnetic moment values (Table 1) of Ce(III) (ground state term: $^2F_{5/2}$), Pr(III) (3H_4), Nd(III)-

* For correspondence.

TABLE I—CHARACTERISATION DATA

Complex	%M	%N	%C	%H	%loss in wt.		Molar cond. (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²) 304°K	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
					120°	200°		
[Y(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	R* 13.01	18.44	42.18	2.95	2.63	—	117	—
[La(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·1.5H ₂ O	F 13.37	18.86	42.50	2.70	2.59	—	116	—
[Ce(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·3H ₂ O	R 19.41	15.65	40.29	3.88	3.77	2.51	118	2.53(297°)
[Pr(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·1.5H ₂ O	F 19.63	15.83	40.70	3.01	3.81	2.33	119	3.62(297°)
[Nd(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·1.5H ₂ O	R 18.84	15.07	38.76	3.66	7.21	2.42	123	3.52(297°)
[Sm(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·2.5H ₂ O	F 18.55	15.16	39.00	3.50	7.01	2.13	120	1.70(297°)
[Gd(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	R 19.64	15.62	40.18	3.37	**	**	124	8.06(306°)
[Tb(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O	F 19.03	15.77	40.40	3.30	—	—	116	10.51(306°)
[Dy(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·0.5C ₂ H ₅ OH	R 20.01	15.55	39.99	3.36	3.74	2.49	120	9.44(306°)
[Ho(PyBzH) ₂ NO ₃ ·OH·H ₂ O]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	F 19.76	15.35	40.00	3.40	3.83	2.37	118	10.56(306°)
[Y(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	R 19.58	14.69	39.10	3.80	**	**	116	10.51(306°)
[La(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	F 19.38	14.86	39.20	3.00	—	—	—	—
[Ce(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·3H ₂ O	R 21.68	15.47	—	—	2.49	2.49	—	—
[Pr(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·1.5H ₂ O	F 21.56	15.64	—	—	2.54	2.62	—	—
[Nd(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·1.5H ₂ O	R 21.30	15.05	—	—	4.80	2.67	—	—
[Sm(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·2.5H ₂ O	F 20.92	15.02	—	—	4.20	2.67	—	—
[Gd(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	R 22.13	15.26	40.87	3.37	3.13	2.45	118	10.56(306°)
[Tb(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O	F 21.90	15.17	41.03	4.41	3.54	2.15	116	10.51(306°)
[Dy(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·0.5C ₂ H ₅ OH	R 22.58	15.30	—	—	2.46	2.46	—	—
[Ho(PyBzH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	F 22.38	15.52	—	—	2.28	2.57	—	—

PyBzH = C₁₂H₉N₃

*R = required, F = found

**Could not be done on account of low yield.

(⁴I_{9/2}), Gd(III) (⁶S_{7/2}), Tb(III) (⁷F₆), Dy(III) (⁶H_{15/2}) and Ho(III) (⁶I₈) agree well with the formula⁷:

$\mu_{eff} = g[J(J+1)]^{1/2}$. The magnetic moment of Sm(III) (⁶H_{5/2}; 1.70 B.M.) is higher than the calculated value of 0.84 B.M. because of the appreciable population in some excited J-levels lying much closer to the ground level⁷.

Infrared spectra: The NH stretching frequency of PyBzH appearing in the region 3150-3030 cm⁻¹ suggests that the imidazole NH remains undeprotonated⁹⁻¹⁰. Broad absorption bands in the region 3525-3200 cm⁻¹ are ascribed to ν (OH) indicating the presence of water (coordinated, uncoordinated or hydrogen-bonded) or alcohol¹¹. Bending mode of H-O-H appears in the range 1640-1615 cm⁻¹ in each compound and that of M-O-H near 1160-1150 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes except that of Y(III).

A coordinated nitrate (C_{2v}) is expected to exhibit six fundamentals¹². The highest frequency band, ν_4 (B₁), appears as a very strong broad multiplet in the range 1530-1435 cm⁻¹, obscuring the weak ligand bands at 1485 and 1460 cm⁻¹. The ν_1 (A₁) mode appears in the range 1350-1298 cm⁻¹ as a strong band in every complex. On the basis of the magnitude of $\nu_4 - \nu_1$ (La: 190, Ce: 200, Pr: 190, Nd: 230, Sm: 190, Y: 175, Gd: 182, Tb: 182, Dy: 175, Ho: 172 cm⁻¹)¹³ and other arguments placed in one of our previous communications¹⁴, we assume that the nitrate is bidentate.

The weak bands at 1040 and 798 cm⁻¹ of PyBzH are highly intensified in the complexes, slightly shifted in position and sometimes accompanied by shoulders or satellites. These are assigned to ν_3 (A₁) and ν_5 (B₂) vibrational modes, respectively, though the latter may very well be treated as ν_4 (E') of the

ionic nitrate, discussed later. The strong absorption band at 740 cm⁻¹ of the organic ligand is shifted slightly to the higher frequency side in the complexes (La: 752, Ce: 745, Pr: 755, Nd: 752, Sm: 755, Y: 755, Gd: 748, Tb: 745, Dy: 745, Ho: 750 cm⁻¹) and shoulders appear in Y-, La-, Ce-, Pr- and Tb-complexes in the range 760-745 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ν_8 (A₁) vibrational mode of the C_{2v}-nitrate. However, in Nd- and Sm-complexes, the main 752 cm⁻¹ band extends with possible multiplets upto 760 cm⁻¹ making it broader. A weak to medium intensity band at 715-700 cm⁻¹ in each of La-, Ce-, Pr-, Nd-, Gd-, Tb-, Dy- and Ho-complexes correspond to ν_6 (B₁) mode of C_{2v}-NO₃.

At least two of the three infrared active fundamentals, expected for uncoordinated nitrate (D_{3h}), are observed. The ν_8 (E') mode appears as shoulder in the range 1400-1372 cm⁻¹. There is an extremely weak absorption in the ligand at 813 cm⁻¹, but in every complex there is a strong band near 820-813 cm⁻¹, which is ascribed to ν_8 (A₁) mode of the D_{3h}-nitrate. It has already been mentioned that 798-795 cm⁻¹ band may be treated as ν_5 (C_{2v}-NO₃) or ν_4 (D_{3h}-NO₃).

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the complexes have been recorded in DMF. The sulphur-yellow Ce(III)-complex shows a strong absorption near 450 nm on account of 4f→5d transition¹⁵.

The ¹G₄(9.80 kK), ³F₄(6.85 kK), ³F₃(6.41 kK), ³F₂(4.69, 4.95, 5.08 kK) and ³H₆(4.46 kK) levels of Pr(III)¹⁶, not located earlier in the aquo-ion^{17,18} or in the terpyridyl system¹⁹, have been located apart from the ³P₂(22.47 kK), ³P₁(21.28 kK), ³P₀(20.70 kK) and ¹D₂(16.81 kK) levels. The

extent of red-shifts suggests a meagre nephelauxetic effect.

The band positions of Nd(III), ${}^4F_{5/2}$ (11.30, 11.51 kK), ${}^4F_{7/2}$ and ${}^2H_{9/2}$ (12.16, 12.50 kK), ${}^4S_{3/2}$ (13.46 kK), ${}^4F_{7/2}$ (13.60 kK), ${}^4F_{9/2}$ (14.81 kK), ${}^2H_{11/2}$ (15.92 kK), ${}^2G_{7/2}$ (17.18 kK), ${}^4G_{5/2}$ (17.48 kK), ${}^4G_{7/2}$ (19.05 kK), ${}^4G_{9/2}$ (19.47 kK), ${}^2D_{5/2}$ (21.05 kK), ${}^4G_{11/2}$ (21.60 kK), ${}^2P_{1/2}$ (23.31 kK) assigned on the basis of calculated^{16,20} and aquo-ion values^{17,18,21} indicate that PyBzH produces even smaller nephelauxetic effect than bipy does²².

The Sm(III) J-levels, ${}^6H_{5/2}$ (6.15-6.63 kK), ${}^6F_{5/2}$ (7.14 kK), ${}^6F_{7/2}$ (7.98 kK), ${}^6F_{9/2}$ (9.17 kK), ${}^6F_{11/2}$ (10.53 kK) and 6P (24.75 kK) have been located as in LaCl_3 -host²³.

The J-levels of Gd(III), all expected in the ultraviolet region²⁴, could not be located on account of strong ligand absorptions in that region.

The bands 7F_2 (4.94, 5.03 kK), 7F_1 (5.35 kK), 5D_3 (26.18 kK) and ${}^5L_{10}$ (27.17 kK) of Tb(III) suffer little red-shift with reference to the positions in LaCl_3 -host²⁵. Again, there are practically no red-shifts in Dy(III) bands²⁶, ${}^6H_{9/2}$ and ${}^6F_{11/2}$ (7.66, 7.72 kK; hypersensitive), ${}^6H_{7/2}$ and ${}^6F_{9/2}$ (9.01 kK), ${}^6H_{5/2}$ (10.20 kK), ${}^6F_{7/2}$ (10.93 kK), ${}^6F_{5/2}$ (12.36 kK) and ${}^6F_{3/2}$ (13.16 kK) and so also in Ho(III) bands²⁷, 5I_7 (4.93 kK), 5I_6 (8.42, 8.51, 8.68 kK), 5I_5 (11.30 kK), 5F_5 (15.50 kK), 5S_2 (18.12 kK), 5F_4 (18.59 kK), 5F_3 (20.66 kK), 5F_2 (21.05 kK), 5K_3 (21.37 kK), 5G_6 or 5F_1 (22.12 kK) and 5G_5 (23.70 kK).

The spectral data thus suggest that the extent of covalency decreases with increasing *f*-orbital occupancy.

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